

D6.7 Final Public Communication Materials

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020- NMBP-ST-IND-2019 – 862192
Project title	SunCoChem: Photoelectrocatalytic device for sun-driven CO ₂ conversion into green chemicals
Duration of the project	May 2020 – October 2024 (54 months)
WP/Task	WP6 / T6.2. T6.4.
Document due Date	31/10/2024
Actual date of delivery	25/10/2024
Leader of this deliverable	EUT
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document status	FINAL

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	11/09/2024	Laura Cercós (EUT)	First draft
0.2	08/10/2024	Míriam Vendrell (EUT)	Review 1 st draft version
0.3	11/10/2024	Laura Cercós (EUT)	Production of final version
0.4	16/10/2024	Angelica Chiodoni (IIT)	Revision
0.5	24/10/2024	Laura Cercós (EUT)	Production of the final version, data updates
1.0	25/10/2024	María Navarro (EUT)	Implementation of changes and production of final version

Executive summary

This deliverable outlines the communication actions done during M23-M54 including the production of promotional materials and videos, project website updates, social media activity and media relations, among others. An evaluation of media impacts, as well as social media statistics, is included in this document.

Table of contents

Deliverable Information sheet	2
Executive summary	2
Table of contents	3
List of figures	4
List of tables	5
List of abbreviations	5
Introduction	6
1. Communication materials	7
1.1 Corporate visual identity (CVI)	7
1.2 Project promotional materials	7
1.2.1 Audiovisual materials	7
1.2.2 Event materials	10
1.3 Public Website	15
1.3.1 Website analytics	16
1.3.2 New pages created	17
1.4 Social Media	26
1.4.1 Twitter	26
1.4.2 LinkedIn	28
1.4.3 YouTube	30
1.4.4 Partners Channels	30
1.5 Media relations	31
1.6 Other Communication Actions	33
1.6.1 Community of Interest	33
1.6.2 ENLIT	34
1.6.3 Green Tech Catalogue	35
2. Communication KPIs	35
3. ANNEX	37
3.1 Articles published in media outlets	37

List of figures

Figure 1: SunCoChem project video.	8
Figure 2: SunCoChem prototype video	8
Figure 3: Final Conference social media banners.	10
<i>Figure 4: Final Conference Flyer</i>	11
Figure 5: Email invite template to the Final Conference.	11
Figure 6: Final Conference program.	12
Figure 7: Final Conference Accreditations.	13
Figure 8: Final Conference directional signs.	13
Figure 9: Final Conference Power Point template.	14
Figure 10: EU Green Week social media banner.	14
Figure 11: Social Media banners for promoting SunCoChem Summer School 2024... 14	14
Figure 12: Initial website structure.....	15
Figure 13: Final website structure, with new pages added in green.	16
Figure 14: World visit distribution for SunCoChem website. (M4 until October 23 rd , 2024 - M54)	17
Figure 15: Project news webpage.....	18
Figure 16: Past events webpage.....	19
Figure 17: Events organised in the website header menu.....	19
Figure 18: From top left to right: Final Conference webpage, EU Green Week Webinar 2022, Summer School 2024 and CEN Workshop.	20
Figure 19: Results section in the header menu.	20
Figure 20: Media Impact webpage, with articles included between M24-M54.	21
Figure 21: Scientific Production webpage.	22
Figure 22: Project Deliverables webpage.....	23
Figure 23: Posters and oral presentations delivered between M24-M54, uploaded in the Project Materials webpage.....	24
Figure 24: Audiovisual materials webpage.....	26
Figure 25: SunCoChem Tweets.....	27
Figure 26: SunCoChem posts on LinkedIn.....	29
Figure 27: SuncoChem YouTube Channel.....	30
Figure 28: Social media posts by SunCoChem partners.	31
Figure 29: SunCoChem first article at the European Energy Innovation magazine.	32
Figure 30: SunCoChem second article at the European Energy Innovation.	33
Figure 31: SunCoChem emailing campaigns to promote Final Conference and Summer School 2024.....	34
Figure 32: SunCoChem ENIL factsheet.	35
Figure 33: The GreenTech Catalogue, by ACCIÓ, with the SunCoChem inclusion.....	35

List of tables

Table 1: Top visited articles and webpages from the SunCoChem Website (August 2020 – M4 until October 23 rd , 2024 - M54)	16
Table 2: Channel types of visits for the SunCoChem website (M4 until October 23 rd , 2024 - M54)	17
Table 3: SunCoChem Twitter Data Analytics (May 2020 – 23 rd October 2024)	28
Table 4: SunCoChem LinkedIn Data Analytics (November 2021 – October 23 rd , 2024)	29
Table 5: SunCoChem YouTube Data Analytics (May 2021 – October 23 rd , 2024).....	30
Table 6: Communication KPIs.....	36
Table 7: SunCoChem Media Clipping (M1- M54* *October 23, 2024).....	37

List of abbreviations

CVI	<i>Corporate Visual Identity</i>
EC	<i>European Commission</i>
EU	<i>European Union</i>
EUT	<i>Eurecat</i>
RCO	<i>Research Communications Office</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>

Introduction

SunCoChem in a nutshell:

SunCoChem has developed a reactor prototype to manufacture chemicals using renewable energies drawing on carbon dioxide (CO₂) recovered from the chemical industry and solar energy.

By achieving this, SunCoChem addresses the need of the European Chemical Industry to reduce their dependence on carbon feedstock by producing highly competitive and integrated solutions enabling the carbon-neutral production of energy and high-value chemicals.

EUT, through its Research Communications Office (RCO), has coordinated the **Task 6.4 Communication Activities**, with the involvement of all consortium partners.

The project's communication plan focuses on creating a variety of digital, printed, and audio-visual materials to support dissemination efforts aimed at both industrial and scientific audiences. Additionally, it includes the establishment and ongoing management of the project's digital channels, such as social media, and its website.

For more information on key messages, target audiences and channels used *please refer to D6.1 and D6.4.*

1. Communication materials

Throughout the lifespan of the project, EUT, as the leader of the Communication & Dissemination task, has created and designed various communication materials, and has conducted numerous communication activities.

During the last two years and a half of the project (M24-M54), communication efforts have been focused on producing **audiovisual materials** showcasing SunCoChem's latest advancements; creating new **promotional materials** for project events and activities; updating the **website** with results and news; generating **social media content**; and enhancing SunCoChem's **media presence**. This deliverable specifically focuses on these communication activities.

For further detailed information on materials and actions developed during M1-M24 period, *please refer to **D6.6 Public Communication Materials***.

1.1 Corporate visual identity (CVI)

The SunCoChem project has consistently maintained its branding elements, which EUT has implemented across various channels and materials to ensure brand consistency and easy recognition. Project partners have also followed the CVI manual throughout their activities.

For further details, *please refer to **D6.1** and **D6.6***

1.2 Project promotional materials

Throughout the project, a set of promotional materials (info-sheet, general poster, general presentation, rollup, trifold and a poster layout) has been created. These materials are available in digital format to consortium members and can be accessed on the SunCoChem website (<https://suncochem.eu/promotional-materials/>). For more detailed information regarding these materials, *please refer to **D6.6***.

The following subsections offer extended details on **audiovisual materials** and **event promotional materials** produced during M24-M54.

1.2.1 Audiovisual materials

During the last 30 months, the SunCoChem project has produced a total of **14 videos** to effectively communicate its advancements, enhance project reach and engage a broader audience.

These videos achieved over **2,000 views** (more detailed metrics available in section **1.4.3**) and are accessible on the SunCoChem website (<https://suncochem.eu/audiovisual-materials/>) and project's social media channels.

1.2.1.1 Project video

The SunCoChem project animated video, released in M25, provides an overview of the project using motion graphics. It contextualizes the need to reduce the European Chemical Industry's dependence on carbon feedstocks, outlines the project's goals, and

showcases its innovative solution for carbon-neutral production of high-value chemicals. The video demonstrates how the photoelectrocatalytic reactor mimics photosynthesis, converting solar energy and CO₂ emissions into valuable oxo-products. With clear and concise language, it targets industry stakeholders, academia, and the general public.

Figure 1: SunCoChem project video.

1.2.1.2 Prototype Final Video

The SunCoChem final video, delivered in M53, consists of a 3D video which showcases how the photoelectrocatalytic reactor developed within the project synthesizes valuable oxo-products from CO₂, H₂O, and solar energy. Utilizing 3D animation, the video illustrates the four processes involved, from the CO₂ capture to the hydroformylation in which obtained syngas (from CO₂ and water) reacts with chemical precursors to produce oxo-products such as Limoxal or Valerdaldehyde.

Figure 2: SunCoChem prototype video

1.2.1.3 Partners interviews

Throughout the project, a total of **9 interview videos** with consortium partners have been produced. These videos, published between M40-M50, convey in-depth information on various project advancements and results.

- *Interview - Alberto Lopera, PhD Researcher, Laurentia Technologies (20 jul 2023)*: On the main challenges in scaling up the production of photo-electrocatalysts and the solutions implemented.
- *Interview - Freddy Liendo, PhD and R&D specialist, Hysytech (20 jul 2023)*: On the key conceptual specifications considered for the project's photoelectrocatalytic reactor.
- *Interview - Fatwa Abdi, Senior Scientist, Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (20 jul 2023)*: On the integration of the photo-electro-anode and electro-cathode in SunCoChem's reactor cells and modules, as well as the lab-scale development and testing.
- *Interview - Miriam Díaz de los Bernardos, Director of the Chemical Technology Unit, Eurecat (27 jul 2023)*: On the photoelectrocatalytic reactor, the key materials used in the CO₂ reduction system, and the project's benefits.
- *Interview - Sara Cavaliere, Lecturer in chemistry and materials science, CNRS (18 ene 2024)*: On the bipolar membrane utilized in the photoelectrocatalytic reactor, including its properties and preparation process.
- *Interview - Bart van den Bosch, Senior Scientist, Avantium (9 feb 2024)*: On the market analysis report on SunCoChem technology and its business potential.
- *Interview - Boyan Iliev, Head of custom synthesis, IoLiTec (25 mar 2024)*: On the importance of Ionic Liquids, as well as scalable synthesis strategies developed.
- *Interview - Simelys Hernández, SunCoChem's technical coordinator, Politecnico di Torino (15 may 2024)*: On the technology developed in the project for treating industrial flue gases.
- *Interview - Angelica Chiodoni, Senior Researcher, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT) (24 may 2024)*: On the operando TEM techniques and their application within the SunCoChem project.

1.2.1.4 Other audiovisual content

Between M25-M54, **4 more videos** were produced and published, including a cluster video, a webinar recording, an event participation and a research and testing demonstration:

- [Road2GreenChem European Cluster - Path towards safe & sustainable chemicals through renewable energy \(17 Feb 2022\)](#)
- [SunCoChem EU Green Week webinar \(1 Jun 2022\)](#)
- [Partners from the Politecnico di Torino present SunCoChem in the European Researchers Night 2022 \(4 Oct 2022\)](#)
- [SunCoChem Research and Testing processes \(20 Sep 2024\)](#)

1.2.2 Event materials

New promotional materials have been created to support the promotion of organized events. These materials include digital invitations, email campaigns, and social media graphics, all designed to enhance engagement and awareness of project activities

1.2.2.1 Final Conference materials

SunCoChem held its final project conference, “Advancing Towards a Carbon-Neutral and Sustainable Chemical Production,” on October 23, 2024. To promote the event, a range of promotional materials was created, along with a dedicated website (see **section 1.3.2.1.3, Events Organised**).

For social media, specific banners were designed announcing the various talks of the Conference.

Figure 3: Final Conference social media banners.

Additionally, a **flyer** was produced for online and offline distribution, and an **email invite** template was provided to partners, with email campaigns conducted by EUT (*refer to section 1.6.1, Community of Interest*). A **program** in PDF format was also created for use before and during the event.

Figure 4: Final Conference Flyer

Figure 5: Email invite template to the Final Conference.

Figure 6: Final Conference program.

For the conference development, participant **accreditations** and **directional signs** were designed and printed, along with **special presentation templates** to ensure a cohesive identity for the speakers.

Figure 7: Final Conference Accreditations.

Figure 8: Final Conference directional signs.

Figure 9: Final Conference Power Point template.

1.2.2.2 Other SunCoChem event materials

Other promotional materials were created to promote the European Green Week Webinar, celebrated in M25, and SunCoChem Summer School, in July 2024 (M51).

Figure 10: EU Green Week social media banner.

Figure 11: Social Media banners for promoting SunCoChem Summer School 2024.

1.3 Public Website

The SunCoChem website serves as a central hub for the project's communication efforts and has been regularly updated since its creation. The initial plan, structure, and content developed during the M1-M24 period were detailed in Deliverables **D6.1** and **D6.6**. Over the past two and half years of the project, the website has experienced the addition of new pages and ongoing content updates, ensuring that it remains relevant and informative.

Figure 12: Initial website structure

Figure 13: Final website structure, with new pages added in green.

1.3.1 Website analytics

Since its launch in M3, the SunCoChem’s website has received a total **14,990 visits**, **32,955 page visits**, **11,463 users** and **2.4 actions per visit**, including page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches per visit (*Data Analytics provided by Matomo from August 2020 – M4 until October 23rd, 2024 - M54*). The most visited sections inside the website include the homepage, the consortium page, general information pages and event information pages.

Table 1: Top visited articles and webpages from the SunCoChem Website (August 2020 – M4 until October 23rd, 2024 - M54)

Top visited articles/webpages	Pageviews
<u>Home</u>	9,577
<u>About SunCoChem project</u>	1,610
<u>SunCoChem Final Conference</u>	1,520
<u>Partners</u>	1,886
<u>Webinar – Photocatalytic synthesis for a carbon-neutral production of fuels and chemicals</u>	862
<u>Solar Driven Chemistry</u>	988

As for **geographical distribution**, the SunCoChem website has been visited from a **huge number of countries in the world**, covering all the continents. Most visits have come from **Spain (4,952)**, followed by visitors from the United States (1,994), Germany (1,547) and Italy (1,498).

Figure 14: World visit distribution for SunCoChem website. (M4 until October 23rd, 2024 - M54)

As for the channel types of traffic, the users mainly entered the SunCoChem website from **direct entry, search engines and social networks**. The most successful network for redirecting traffic to the website was LinkedIn, highlighting the success of the EUT strategy in that network (see section **1.4.2 LinkedIn** for more details).

Table 2: Channel types of visits for the SunCoChem website (M4 until October 23rd, 2024 - M54)

Channel type	Visits
Direct entry	8,832
Search engines	3,646
Social networks	LinkedIn: 1,295
	Twitter: 488
	Facebook: 175

1.3.2 New pages created

Throughout the project lifespan, the SunCoChem’s website has incorporated new webpages as well as new articles.

1.3.2.1 News & Events

All the information related to project news and events either organised and participated by the consortium partners are allocated under the section “News & Events”. This section has been slightly modified and it is now separated in the pages “Project News”, “Past Events”, as well as some special pages for the events organised (Final Event, Summer Schools...).

1.3.2.1.1 Project news

Since its creation, up to October 23rd, 2024 (M54), **9 articles were published in this page**, including news on the Final Press release, the EU Green Week 2022 webinar, SunCoChem meetings and the draft CEN Workshop Agreement.

Figure 15: Project news webpage.

1.3.2.1.2 Past events

A total of **68 articles were published in this section**, up to October 23rd, 2024 (M54), including information about fairs and exhibitions, project meetings, scientific conferences, workshops, summer schools and clustering events, among others.

The *Past events* webpage also includes an updated agenda for informing about future events.

Figure 16: Past events webpage.

1.3.2.1.3 Events organised

For each event organised within the project, a dedicated webpage has been created. Unlike the initial website structure, in which all SunCoChem events were listed under a single *Events organised* webpage, the website has been updated to make the events more visible and accessible. All the events pages are now included in the header menu, inside the *News & Events* section.

Figure 17: Events organised in the website header menu.

The webpages created include the Final Conference webpage, SunCoChem Webinars (EU Green Week 2021, Photocatalytic Synthesis Webinar 2021, EU Green Week 2022), SunCoChem Summer Schools (2020, 2021, 2024), and the Standardisation CEN workshop.

Figure 18: From top left to right: Final Conference webpage, EU Green Week Webinar 2022, Summer School 2024 and CEN Workshop.

1.3.2.2 Results section

The results section has been regularly updated with **new media impacts, materials, scientific production and deliverables**.

Figure 19: Results section in the header menu.

1.3.2.2.1 Media impacts

A total of **13 articles** featuring SunCoChem were updated at the *Media Impacts* webpage, 5 of them included between M24-M54 (23rd October 2024). This website section also includes a full clipping study and 2 press releases. **For more information on articles published and media relations, see section 1.5.**

The screenshot shows the SunCoChem website's media impact page. At the top, there are social media icons for X, YouTube, and LinkedIn, along with the email address info@suncochem.eu. The SunCoChem logo is on the left, and a search bar and a 'CONTACT US' button are on the right. A navigation menu includes Home, About SunCoChem, Solar-driven chemistry, Partners, News & Events, Results, Road2GreenChem Cluster, and Contact. The main heading is 'SUNCOCHEM IN THE NEWS'. Below it, a sub-heading reads 'See below a selection of articles featuring SunCoChem:'. Five articles are listed, each with a logo, date, publication name, and a brief description:

- diari més** (October 23, 2024): Creen un prototipo de reactor para fabricar productos químicos utilizando energías renovables (Spanish)
- SOLARNEWS** (October 23, 2024): Presentan un nuevo dispositivo que recupera las emisiones de CO₂ de la industria para fabricar productos químicos más sostenibles (Spanish)
- European Energy Innovation** (October 2024): Photoelectrocatalytic device to achieve carbon-neutral chemical production: the SunCoChem solution (English)
- European Energy Innovation** (June 2024): Advancing towards carbon-neutral energy and high-value chemical production (English)
- Interempresas** (April 01, 2023): Eurecat ensaya tecnologías de descarbonización para capturar dióxido de carbono y potenciar su recuperación para la generación de nuevos productos (Spanish)

Figure 20: Media Impact webpage, with articles included between M24-M54.

1.3.2.2.2 Scientific production

A total of **13 scientific publications** related to SunCoChem project have been uploaded in this section, as well as in the project's **Zenodo Community**. Ten of them have been produced and uploaded during M24-M54. One additional publication, at present in preparation, is planned also after the conclusion of the project.

The screenshot shows the 'SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION' section of the SunCO2Chem website. At the top, there are social media icons (Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn) and an email address 'info@suncochem.eu'. Below this is the SunCO2Chem logo, a search bar, and a 'CONTACT US' button. A navigation menu includes links for Home, About SunCoChem, Solar-driven chemistry, Partners, News & Events, Results, Road2GreenChem Cluster, and Contact. The main heading is 'SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION', followed by a sub-heading: 'In this page you will be able to find the scientific publications related to SunCoChem project published by partners'. The content is organized into several article cards, each with a title, a date, a brief description, and a 'READ MORE' button. The visible titles include: 'Standardization of Cu2O nanocubes synthesis...', 'Cu2O/SnO2 Heterostructures: Role of the Synthesis Procedure...', 'Cosmetics and Detergents with Recycled CO2: A Cross-Country Study...', 'Climate change risk perception and intentions to buy consumer packaged goods...', 'Understanding the role of imidazolium-based ionic liquids in the electrochemical CO2 reduction reaction', and 'Solar-driven CO2 reduction catalysed by hybrid supramolecular photocathodes...'. The 'READ MORE' buttons are highlighted in orange.

Figure 21: Scientific Production webpage.

1.3.2.2.3 Deliverables

This web section includes all the deliverables submitted. Public deliverables have been uploaded on full, while the confidential ones have been published only including the executive summary. A total of **24 deliverables** have been uploaded during M24-M54 period.

The screenshot shows the 'PROJECT DELIVERABLES' section of the SunCO₂Chem website. It features a navigation bar with links for Home, About SunCoChem, Solar-driven chemistry, Partners, News & Events, Results, Road2GreenChem Cluster, and Contact. A search bar and a 'CONTACT US' button are also present. The main content is organized into two work packages (WPs):

- WP1 – Development of Photo-Electrochemical Cell Materials**
 - D1.1 Hybrid PECats concept and performance specifications – Executive Summary** (1 file(s), 192 KB) [Download]
 - D1.2 – Preliminary selection of the anode and cathode PECats composition – Executive Summary** (1 file(s), 183.64 KB) [Download]
 - D1.3 Synthesis of the selected anode and cathode hybrid multifunctional PECats for TRL3 cell optimization – Executive Summary** (1 file(s), 193.34 KB) [Download]
 - D1.4 Scale up process for PECats synthesis – Executive Summary** (1 file(s), 178.44 KB) [Download]
 - D1.5 Optimum photo-electrodes selected and report on the performance – Executive Summary** (1 file(s), 195.49 KB) [Download]
- WP2 – Development of Proton Transport, CO₂ Capture and Concentration Cell Materials**
 - D2.1 – TBM and the CO₂ capture and concentration stage concept and specifications – Executive Summary** (1 file(s), 0.00 KB) [Download]

Figure 22: Project Deliverables webpage.

1.3.2.2.4 Project materials

This webpage includes the project's promotional materials, along with the different presentations and posters presented by partners in exhibitions, congresses, international conferences and other key events. A total of **10 posters and oral presentations delivered by partners** were included during M24-M54 period.

The screenshot shows the SunCoChem website's 'Posters and presentations delivered' section. It lists 16 items, each with a title, a PDF icon, a file size, and a 'Download' button. The items are organized into sections based on the event they were presented at.

- Section 1: SunCoChem poster presented during the Convegno Linceo su Combustibili di sintesi (e-fuels) - October 2024**
 - Convegno Linceo su Combustibili di sintesi (e-fuels) - Poster (1 MB, 20.95 KB)
- Section 2: SunCoChem presentation delivered during the 2nd FlowPhotoChem's Exploitation Workshop - September 2024**
 - Flow PhotoChem workshop presentation: "Scaling-up a Photo-electrocatalytic System for CO2 Capture and Conversion to Oxo-products: the SunCoChem approach" (1 MB, 20.95 KB)
- Section 3: Poster showcased during the annual Electrochemical Society Meeting - May 2024**
 - ECS Meeting 2024 poster "Bipolar membranes for photoelectrochemical CO2 conversion" (1 MB, 20.95 KB)
- Section 4: Project presentation showcased during the European Marketing Academy's Regional Conference (EMAC) - September 2023**
 - Climate Change Risk Perceptions in a VBN Model to Predict Intentions to Buy Cosmetics and Detergents Containing Recycled CO2 (1 MB, 955.65 KB)
- Section 5: SunCoChem presentation delivered during the SUNER-C project powered by the SUNERGY Community - June 2023**
 - PhotoElectroCatalytic Device for Sun Driven CO2 conversion into Green Chemicals (1 MB, 955.65 KB)
- Section 6: Poster presented during the the 15th Mediterranean Congress in Chemical Engineering (MECCÉ) - June 2023**
 - Supported Imidazolium Based Ionic Liquids on a Polysulfone Matrix for Enhanced CO2 Capture (1 MB, 955.65 KB)
- Section 7: Poster presented during the Solar2Chem Winter School - February 2023**
 - Scalable Synthesis of Stable Core-Shell Cu2O/SnO2 Nanoparticles For The Electrochemical CO2 Conversion (1 MB, 1.13 MB)
- Section 8: Poster presented during the Green Chemistry Gordon Research Conference - July 2022**
 - Solar-driven CO2 reduction catalysed by Hybrid Supramolecular Photocathodes and enhanced by Ionic Liquids (1 MB, 1.13 MB)
- Section 9: SunCoChem project presented in a SUNERGY Workshop on future solar fuels and chemicals - June 2022**
 - SunCoChem presentation - Shaping the future: renewable fuels and chemicals from solar energy (1 MB, 1.13 MB)
- Section 10: Poster presented in the European Conference on Solar Chemistry and Photocatalysis (SPEA) - June 2022**
 - Solar-driven CO2 reduction catalysed by Molecular Photocathode in aqueous solution (1 MB, 1.13 MB)

Figure 23: Posters and oral presentations delivered between M24-M54, uploaded in the Project Materials webpage.

1.3.2.2.5 Audiovisual Materials

All 16 videos produced within the SunCoChem project have been uploaded to the website, including the 14 videos from the M24-M54 period and the 2 videos created earlier in the project. These audiovisual materials are organized into subsections: general project videos, interviews, and event recordings.

[X](#) [in](#) [info@suncochem.eu](#)

[Home](#) [About SunCoChem](#) [Sole-driven chemistry](#) [Partners](#) [News & Events](#) [Results](#) [Road2GreenChem Cluster](#) [Contact](#)

AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS

In this page you will be able to find all the videos related to SunCoChem project published in our Youtube channel

SunCoChem project video

SunCoChem prototype video

Road2GreenChem cluster video

PARTNERS INTERVIEWS

<p>Interview - Miriam Diaz de la Barina</p> <p>Watch on YouTube</p>	<p>Interview - Simayra Hernández, SunCoChem</p> <p>Watch on YouTube</p>
<p>Interview - Freddy Llerdo, PhD and R...</p> <p>Watch on YouTube</p>	<p>Interview - Fatma Abul, Senior Scien...</p> <p>Watch on YouTube</p>
<p>Interview - Sara Cavallaro, Lecturer L...</p> <p>Watch on YouTube</p>	<p>Interview - Boyan Pan, Head of qual...</p> <p>Watch on YouTube</p>
<p>Interview - Bart van den Bosch, Seni...</p> <p>Watch on YouTube</p>	<p>Interview - Alberto Lopez, PhD Rese...</p> <p>Watch on YouTube</p>

Figure 24: Audiovisual materials webpage.

1.4 Social Media

SunCoChem social media accounts, including the Twitter profile [@SunCoChem_EU](#), [LinkedIn profile](#) and [YouTube channel](#), have been regularly updated, and collectively hold more than **1,000 followers and subscribers**.

For more details about the social media strategy, please refer to **D6.1 Dissemination & Communication Plan** and **D6.6 Public Communication Materials**.

1.4.1 Twitter

EUT continued a monthly social media content plan for Twitter that included a variety of posts such as curated news and information related to project topics, updates on partner participation in events, dissemination of consortium meeting outcomes, promotion of the community of interest sign-up form, distribution of promotional materials, among others.

SunCoChem H2020 Project
@SunCoChem_EU

Join us on October 23 for the [#SunCoChem](#) Closing Event, showcasing cutting-edge innovations for a carbon-neutral EU! ⚡

Don't miss out on sustainable solutions reshaping the [#ChemicalIndustry](#) 🌱

Check out the agenda cutt.ly/SunCoChem_Conf...

Eurecat and 9 others

10:32 AM · Sep 17, 2024 · 533 Views

View post engagements

5 5

SunCoChem H2020 Project
@SunCoChem_EU

⚡ Excited to announce our keynote speaker at the [#SunCoChem](#) closing conference!

Julio Lloret Fillol, group leader at [@ICIQchem](#) will join us delivering the presentation "Artificial Photosynthesis Towards Sustainable Chemical Production"

Don't miss it! cutt.ly/SunCoChem_Conf...

9:32 AM · Sep 26, 2024 · 1,384 Views

View post engagements

3 10

SunCoChem H2020 Project
@SunCoChem_EU

⚡ This week [@Eurecat_news](#), project's coordinator, highlighted [#SunCoChem](#) at the Demo Day organised by [@xarxaH2CAT](#)

[#SunCoChemproject](#) was highlighted as one of Eurecat's key European research and innovation projects in the [#sustainablechemistry](#) sector

suncochem.eu/eurecat-showca...

Universitat de Girona and Clúster de l'Energia Eficient de Catalunya

8:11 AM · Sep 20, 2024 · 89 Views

View post engagements

2 3

SunCoChem H2020 Project
@SunCoChem_EU

NEW VIDEO | How the [#SunCoChem](#)'s photoelectrocatalytic device works?

Our latest video breaks down the complete process of how we use solar energy & CO2 to create oxo-products.

Watch it now

youtube.com
SunCoChem photoelectrocatalytic device to achieve carbon
SunCoChem project has developed a photoelectrocatalytic reactor to synthesize valuable chemical oxo-products, ...

8:51 AM · Sep 25, 2024 · 233 Views

View post engagements

3 5

Figure 25: SunCoChem Tweets.

At M54 (October 23rd, 2024), the SunCoChem Twitter account has **499 followers** and **has published 817 tweets, achieving over 257K impressions**. The project's Twitter metrics have exceeded by far the end-of-project targets.

Table 3: SunCoChem Twitter Data Analytics (May 2020 – 23rd October 2024)

SunCoChem Twitter Account	M54 (23 rd Oct. 2024)	Target by the end of the project
Followers	499	100
Total Tweets	817	200
Impressions	257,279	50,000
Likes on Tweets	1,597	100
Retweets	786	30
Mentions	173	20

This platform has served as a valuable network for extending our reach by connecting with similar projects, initiatives, and individuals. However, changes in Twitter ownership and algorithm adjustments have impacted project's visibility, resulting in a significant decline in impressions and engagement in recent months compared to the metrics recorded before M30. Nevertheless, this has not jeopardized the achievement of the target KPIs by the end of the project.

1.4.2 LinkedIn

Similar to Twitter, EUT implemented a monthly social media content plan for LinkedIn. However, LinkedIn's lack of character limits allowed for more detailed posts, enabling the team to target professionals with a more formal and in-depth tone.

Figure 26: SunCoChem posts on LinkedIn.

As for M54 (October 23rd, 2024), the SunCoChem LinkedIn account counts with **576 followers and has generated 243 posts and more than 72K impressions**. The project’s LinkedIn metrics have also exceeded by far the end-of-project targets.

No major changes in the social media platform nor in its algorithm affected the project’s performance and visibility. SunCoChem’s LinkedIn profile allowed us to create a community of professionals working in related fields, and has been the main source of social network traffic to the project’s website (see Table 2).

Table 4: SunCoChem LinkedIn Data Analytics (November 2021 – October 23rd, 2024)

SunCoChem LinkedIn profile	M54 (October 23 rd , 2024)	Target by the end of the project
Followers	576	150
Total posts	243	50
Impressions	72,837	10,000
Likes/Reactions	2,199	100

1.4.3 YouTube

YouTube, mainly used as a repository of videos, allocates all the **16 videos** produced during the project (for details about each video, see *section 1.2.1 Audiovisual Materials*)

Figure 27: SuncoChem YouTube Channel.

As for M54 (October 23rd, 2024), the SunCoChem YouTube channel account counts with **25 subscribers, 16 videos and more than 2,300 views.**

Table 5: SunCoChem YouTube Data Analytics (May 2021 – October 23rd, 2024)

SunCoChem YouTube profile	M54 (23 rd October 2024)	Target by the end of the project
Videos	16	10
Video views	2,470	100

1.4.4 Partners Channels

Partners used their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook, mainly) to share SunCoChem news and results including press releases, news about events, promotional materials and other contents.

From M1 to M54 (October 23rd, 2024), partners have posted a total of **168 posts in their corporate social media accounts, accumulating 1,246 likes and 103 shares/retweets.**

Figure 28: Social media posts by SunCoChem partners.

1.5 Media relations

SunCoChem's media relations consisted in producing press releases and articles and identifying general and specialised media contacts.

EUT produced the **first SunCoChem press release** with general information about the project and its consortium. For more details about its content and media impacts, please refer to **D6.6 Public Communication Materials**. In total, within all the project's execution SunCoChem consortium has produced a total of **8 press releases**.

These publications have been actively disseminated through Social Media channels and had a significant impact on online and print media.

Press releases produced include:

- **November 2020** - *Chemical industry CO₂ to be recovered to make new products.*
[Read it here.](#)

- **November 2020** - *Recuperarán el CO₂ de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos (also in Catalan). [Read it here.](#)*
- **June 2021** - *Environmental awareness is driving force for recovery across all economic sectors (also in Spanish and Catalan). [Read it here.](#)*
- **January 2023** - *Eurecat ensaya tecnologías de descarbonización para capturar dióxido de carbono y potenciar su recuperación para la generación de nuevos productos (also in Catalan). [Read it here.](#)*
- **October 2024** - *Transforming industrial CO₂ emissions into sustainable chemical products. [Read it here.](#)*
- **October 2024** - *Presenten un nou dispositiu que recupera les emissions de CO₂ de la indústria per fabricar productes químics més sostenibles (in Catalan and also in Spanish). [Read it here.](#)*

Additionally, the SunCoChem project and its results were highlighted in **2 articles** published in **European Energy Innovation**, a specialised magazine for energy, transport, and sustainability stakeholders in Europe. For over 13 years, this magazine has connected researchers, policymakers, officials, and business leaders across various levels.

The first SunCoChem article, entitled **“SunCoChem Project: Carbon-Neutral production for the European Chemical Industry through innovative Photoelectrocatalytic Reactor Technology”**, was published in the Summer 2024 edition, both [online](#) and [printed](#). It focused on presenting SunCoChem’s project and its goals.

Figure 29: SunCoChem first article at the European Energy Innovation magazine.

The second article, entitled **“Photoelectrocatalytic device to achieve carbon-neutral chemical production: the SunCoChem solution”**, has been published in the Autumn

2024 edition, both [online](#) and [printed](#). The focus of this article is explaining how the photoelectrocatalytic device works.

Communication

Photoelectrocatalytic device to achieve carbon-neutral chemical production: the SunCoChem solution

Developing a greener and sustainable process to produce high-value oxo-chemicals for the industry

The European Climate Law sets the target of net zero greenhouse gas emissions, writing into legislation the objective outlined in the European Green Deal: achieving climate neutrality for Europe's economy and society by 2050.

To achieve carbon neutrality in the chemical industry, one of the European Union's primary goals, the SunCoChem EU-funded project is working on a groundbreaking photoelectrocatalytic reactor.

This solution produces valuable chemicals using solar energy and carbon dioxide (CO₂) sourced from chemical industry. SunCoChem's innovative approach not only facilitates the production of essential chemicals but also contributes significantly to the carbon neutrality of the industry.

Ensuring carbon neutrality
Achieving carbon neutrality in the chemical industry requires both decarbonization and defossilization. Decarbonization focuses on reducing carbon dioxide emissions by using low-carbon energy sources and improving energy efficiency. Simultaneously, defossilization seeks to eliminate the use of fossil fuels as a carbon source, replacing them with sustainable and renewable alternatives.

“SunCoChem represents a significant leap towards a sustainable future in energy and chemical production”

The technology developed by SunCoChem focuses on the generation of Limoxal™, a material sold by IFF as a perfuming agent and used in personal care and household cleaning products. Life cycle assessment studies have shown that this reactor can reduce carbon emissions by 10% compared to current fossil fuel-based methods, due to its reliance on renewable carbon sources.

Integrating three key processes
SunCoChem takes inspiration from the natural process of photosynthesis. In photosynthesis, solar energy is used to transform water and CO₂ into new compounds, demonstrating nature's efficient method of harnessing sunlight to drive chemical reactions.

The reactor developed by SunCoChem stands out due to its integration of three critical processes. First, it captures CO₂ from flue gases using selective patented membranes, generating a concentrated CO₂ stream. Second, this CO₂ is converted into syngas (a mixture of CO and H₂) through a photoelectrocatalytic reaction. Finally, the syngas is used in hydroformylation reactions with olefins to produce the desired oxo-chemicals. At laboratory scale, using a solar simulator, the system achieved 8% of solar-to-product efficiency.

Validation and Demonstration
With the final pilot designed and the entire process fully engineered, the construction of the reactor, boasting an impressive active area of 2000 cm², is now underway.

Future efforts will focus on rigorous testing of the reactor using a simulated gas mixture and the abundant energy of natural sunlight. The evaluation

will encompass not only production efficiency but also techno-economic, environmental, societal, and market impacts, offering a comprehensive assessment of the technology's potential.

The SunCoChem project is more than just a technological advancement; it is a paradigm shift in how we approach chemical production. By integrating innovative processes and leveraging renewable resources, SunCoChem is setting a new standard for sustainability in the chemical industry. As the project moves forward, its potential to transform the industry and contribute to global carbon neutrality goals becomes increasingly apparent. ■

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 862192.

European Energy Innovation | Autumn 2024 | 27

Figure 30: SunCoChem second article at the European Energy Innovation.

From M1 to M54 (October 23rd, 2024), the SunCoChem project was featured in **58 media articles**, both in print and online, across general and specialized outlets (see [Table 6 in Annex 3.1](#)).

1.6 Other Communication Actions

1.6.1 Community of Interest

EUT established the **SunCoChem Community of Interest** using MailChimp to build a database of users interested in the project's developments and events. The GDPR-compliant sign-up form was regularly promoted through social media and was also made

available on the project website. *For more information on the sign-up form and the social media campaigns to promote it, please refer to D6.6.*

Thanks to the actions done to promote the community, at M54 (October 23rd, 2024) it is formed by **302 subscribers**. A total of **7 mailing campaigns** were sent to the subscribers list promoting events such as the Final Conference, Summer Schools and webinars, and sharing post-event materials.

Figure 31: SunCoChem emailing campaigns to promote Final Conference and Summer School 2024.

1.6.2 ENLIT

EUT also worked to have SunCoChem featured on the **Enlit collaborative platform** (<https://www.enlit.world/projects/suncochem/>). Enlit is a growing, inclusive, end-to-end forum that brings together people and projects to address every aspect of the energy agenda and drive the energy transition forward.

The SunCoChem factsheet includes project details, a general overview and the website link to the project's website.

Figure 32: SunCoChem ENIL factsheet.

1.6.3 Green Tech Catalogue

EUT also worked to have SunCoChem featured on The Green Tech Catalogue by ACCIÓ, Catalonia Trade & Investment (Government of Catalonia).

Figure 33: The GreenTech Catalogue, by ACCIÓ, with the SunCoChem inclusion.

2. Communication KPIs

A continuous record of the key performance Indicators (KPIs) has been kept in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the actions done. The following table compares the KPIs achieved by M54* (*October 23, 2024) compared to the ones established at the beginning of the project to be achieved by the end of the project.

As shown in the table, the website and social media KPIs achieved successfully the targeted indicators.

Table 6: Communication KPIs

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	M54 (October 23 rd , 2024)	Target by the end of the project
Website	Number of website visits	Matomo Analytics	14,990	>4,000
	Number of pages viewed		32,955	>15,000
	Number of users		11,463	>2,000
	Average session time		2 min 36s	>1 min
	Number actions / session		2.4	>1.5
Social Media - Twitter	Twitter: Number of followers	Twitter Analytics	499	>100
	Twitter: Number of tweets		817	>200
	Twitter: Twitter impressions		257,279	>50,000
	Twitter: Likes on tweets		1,597	>100
	Twitter: Retweets		786	>30
	Twitter: Mentions		173	>20
Social Media – LinkedIn	LinkedIn: Number of followers	LinkedIn Analytics	576	>150
	LinkedIn: Number of posts		243	>50
	LinkedIn: Number of impressions		72,837	>10,000
	LinkedIn: likes/reactions		2,199	>100
Social Media – YouTube	YouTube: Number of videos uploaded	YouTube Analytics	16	>10
	YouTube: Number of video views		2,470	>100
Social Media – Partners	Number of posts	Monthly follow up (quantitative)	168	>20
	Number of likes		1,246	>50
	Number of Shares / Retweets		103	>50
Media Relations	Number of press releases	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	8	>4
	Articles published in media outlets		58	>20
Visual Materials	Number of posters produced	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	10	>2
	Audiovisual materials		16	12

3. ANNEX

3.1 Articles published in media outlets

Table 7: SunCoChem Media Clipping (M1- M54* *October 23, 2024)

Date	Media	Title	Typology	Link
24/10/2024	Energética	Un nuevo dispositivo permite utilizar las emisiones de CO ₂ de la industria para fabricar productos químicos	Online	Link
24/10/2024	La Vanguardia	Crean un prototipo de reactor para fabricar productos químicos con energías renovables	Online	Link
24/10/2024	Ecoticias	Proyecto SunCoChem, fabricar productos químicos utilizando energías renovables	Online	Link
23/10/2024	Industria Química	Presentan un nuevo dispositivo que recupera las emisiones de CO ₂ de la industria para fabricar productos químicos más sostenibles	Online	Link
23/10/2024	Diari Més	Crean un prototip de reactor per fabricar productes químics utilitzant energies renovables	Online	Link
23/10/2024	Diari Més	Crean un prototipo de reactor para fabricar productos químicos utilizando energías renovables	Online	Link
23/10/2024	SolarNews	Presentan un nuevo dispositivo que recupera las emisiones de CO ₂ de la industria para fabricar productos químicos más sostenibles	Online	Link
18/10/2024	European Energy Innovation	Photoelectrocatalytic device to achieve carbon-neutral chemical production: the SunCoChem solution	Online	Link
06/01/2024	European Energy Innovation	Advancing towards carbon-neutral energy of high-value chemical production	Online	Link
18/05/2023	Industria Química	La descarbonización de la industria química y el hidrógeno verde	Online	Link
04/06/2023	Diari de Tarragona	Tarragona brilla en Expoquimia	Print	Link
05/06/2023	Diari de Tarragona	Tarragona brilla en Expoquimia	Online	Link
29/05/2023	Portal de la Industria Química	La innovación y la transferencia tecnológica se dan cita en Expoquimia y Equiplast	Online	Link
29/05/2023	Auto Revista	Expoquimia y Equiplast abren sus puertas hasta el 2 de junio	Online	Link
26/05/2023	La Vanguardia	Expoquimia y Equiplast tendrán un área dedicada a innovación y transferencia tecnológica	Online	Link
26/05/2023	Mundo Compresor	Expoquimia y Equiplast dedican un área a la innovación y transferencia tecnológica	Online	Link
26/05/2023	Retema - Revista Técnica del Medio Ambiente	Expoquimia y Equiplast acogerán 590 expositores de 15 países	Online	Link
26/05/2023	FarmEspaña Industrial	Expoquimia presenta una zona dedicada a la innovación y transferencia tecnológica	Online	Link
26/05/2023	SumIndustria	Expoquimia y Equiplast dedican un área a la innovación y transferencia tecnológica	Online	Link
26/05/2023	Auto Revista	Expoquimia y Equiplast dedican un área a la innovación y transferencia tecnológica	Online	Link
01/02/2023	Interempresas Industria Química	EURECAT ENSAYA TECNOLOGÍAS DE DESCARBONIZACIÓN PARA CAPTURAR DIÓXIDO DE CARBONO Y POTENCIAR SU RECUPERACIÓN PARA LA GENERACIÓN DE NUEVOS PRODUCTOS	Print	Link
15/02/2023	InterEmpresas Energías	Eurecat ensaya tecnologías de descarbonización para capturar dióxido de	Online	Link

		carbono y potenciar su recuperación para la generación de nuevos productos		
29/01/2023	Diari MÉS	Eurecat desenvolupa un reactor per fabricar productes químics amb energia renovable basada en CO2	Online	Link
29/01/2023	Diari MÉS	Eurecat desarrolla un reactor para fabricar productos químicos con energía renovable basada en CO2	Online	Link
28/01/2023	Món Sostenible	En el dia Mundial de la Reducció d'Emissions de CO2 donem consells per reduir les emissions i expliquem assajos tecnològics de descarbonització	Online	Link
28/01/2023	SumIndustria	Eurecat ensaya tecnologías de descarbonización para capturar dióxido de carbono y potenciar su recuperación para la generación de nuevos productos	Online	Link
28/01/2023	EbreDigital	El centre tecnològic tarragoní Eurecat assaja com capturar CO2 de la indústria química	Online	Link
27/01/2023	La Vanguardia	Eurecat assaja com capturar CO2 de la indústria química i un dispositiu que el captura de l'atmosfera	Online	Link
27/01/2023	Nació Digital Tarragona	Eurecat assaja com capturar CO2 de la indústria química i de l'atmosfera	Online	Link
27/01/2023	Regió 7	Eurecat assaja com capturar CO2 de la indústria química i un dispositiu que el captura de l'atmosfera	Online	Link
27/01/2023	Solar News	EURECAT ENSAYA TECNOLOGÍAS DE DESCARBONIZACIÓN PARA CAPTURAR DIÓXIDO DE CARBONO	Online	Link
23/11/2021	Diari Més	Solar, circular i col·laborativa: així serà la química	Print	Link
6/10/2021	ECOticias.com	Medio Ambiente, un potentísimo motor de recuperación en todos los sectores económicos	Online	Link
14/09/2021	Diari de Tarragona	Objetivo: conseguir cero emisiones en 2050	Print	Link
14/09/2021	Diari de Tarragona	Apuesta por la circularidad, sostenibilidad y digitalización de la tecnología química	Print	Link
06/07/2021	InterEmpresas Net	El interés por el medio ambiente, motor de recuperación en todos los sectores económicos	Online	Link
29/03/2021	Diari de Tarragona	Los centros de investigación, la base	Online	Link
26/03/2021	Diari de Tarragona	Los centros de investigación, la base	Print	Link
06/03/2021	Factoria del Futuro	El interés por el medio ambiente, motor de recuperación en todos los sectores económicos	Online	Link
02/01/2021	InterEmpresas Industria Química	La industria química recuperará el CO2 para generar nuevos productos	Print	Link
04/12/2020	Envasprés	Unprecedented Virtual Forum presenta el proyecto SunCoChem	Online	Link
30/11/2020	30Virtual	Eurecat coordina el projecte europeu SunCoChem per recuperar el CO2 de la indústria química per a la generació de nous productes	Online	Link
30/11/2020	Change2Grow (C2G)	Recuperarán el CO2 de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos	Online	Link
29/11/2020	La Vanguardia	La industria química vol utilitzar el seu propi CO2	Print	Link
25/11/2020	Residuos Profesional	El proyecto SunCoChem recuperará el CO2 de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos	Online	Link
24/11/2020	Izaro	El proyecto SunCoChem recuperará el CO2 de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos	Online	Link

23/11/2020	Automatica e instrumentacion	Un proyecto coordinado por Eurecat recupera el CO2 de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos	Online	Link
23/11/2020	Retema	El proyecto SunCoChem permitirá recuperar el CO2 en plantas químicas para la generación de nuevos productos	Online	Link
21/11/2020	Factoria del Futuro	Recuperación del CO2 de la industria química para generar nuevos productos	Online	Link
20/11/2020	Revista PQ	Alternativa sostenible a la producción de productos químicos con combustibles fósiles	Online	Link
20/11/2020	El Confidencial Químico	Eurecat presenta el proyecto SunCoChem con la propuesta de una alternativa	Online	Link
20/11/2020	InterEmpresas	La industria química recuperará el CO2 para generar nuevos productos	Online	Link
20/11/2020	El Punt Avui	Recuperar el CO2 de la indústria química per fer-ne nous productes	Online	Link
20/11/2020	L'Econòmic	Recuperar el CO2 de la indústria química per fer-ne nous productes	Online	Link
19/11/2020	Buenaquímica.org	Nace un proyecto que recuperará el CO2 de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos	Online	Link
19/11/2020	ABC.es	Eurecat generará nuevos productos a partir del CO2 de la industria química	Online	Link
19/11/2020	La Vanguardia	Eurecat generará nuevos productos a partir del CO2 de la industria química	Online	Link
10/06/2020	AEQT	DOW participa en el proyecto europeo SunCoChem	Online	Link